

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART IV. INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE

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Influence of temperature t on the Joshi effect Δi in oxygen, enclosed in a (sealed) Siemens' type glass ozoniser at 331 mm. pressure (32°), has been studied over 30° to 125° and 2 to 5 kilo-volts of 50 cycles frequency. At a constant applied V, the discharge current i increases markedly with t . The increase with t of the mobility of ions has been shown to be small. The current rise is attributed therefore to the increase with t of the dielectric conductivity, and from Joshi's equation of the dielectric constant, of glass. The net effect Δi at constant V increases with t up to 50° and then decreases. The relative effect $\% \Delta i$, on the other hand, decreases progressively. According to Joshi, formation on the excited electrodes of a boundary layer derived, in part, from a wall-adsorption of ions and other particles in the discharge space is primary to Δi . Electrons released from this layer on irradiation are captured by the electro-negative gas-elements to form negative ions which produce Δi . Temperature would cause desorption and depolarization of the particles constituting the boundary layer, and would inhibit negative ion formation. Decrease of Δi , as observed, follows.

The marked dependence of the magnitude of the Joshi effect Δi on temperature t has been pointed out by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75). Joshi and Kuppuswamy (*ibid.*, 1941, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 35) found that Δi in chlorine decreases with t . Essentially similar were the observations of Deo and co-workers (Deo and Padmanabhulu, *ibid.*, 1944, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 36; Deo and Uis, *ibid.*, 1945, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 16) in chlorine, of Subba Rao and Shanmukha Rao (*ibid.*, 1944, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 37) in hydrochloric acid gas, and of Lahiry (*ibid.*, 1945, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 27) in iodine vapour in equilibrium with the solid. In view of the absence, apart from the preliminary observations of the author (*ibid.*, 1948, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 13), of data in the literature of this Δi phenomenon on the influence of temperature on the Joshi effect in oxygen, it was of interest to extend the above work to this gas, activated by the silent discharge.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement and the electrical circuit are shown in Fig. 1. A sealed Siemens' type glass ozoniser containing purified oxygen at 331 mm. pressure (32°) constituted the discharge vessel. It was enclosed in an asbestos-lined wooden box which had a glass window on one side. The interior of the box was heated electrically, temperature being regulated by varying the current through the heating coils. Temperature was recorded at three different positions with thermometers T_1 , T_2 and T_3 , and was kept constant at a desired value for at least 30 minutes before commencing a series of Δi observations.

The high tension terminal of the ozoniser was represented by mercury contained in the

FIG. 1

inner tube. A helix of copper wire (the distance between consecutive turns being sufficiently large to permit irradiation of the enclosed gas) on the outer tube constituted the low tension terminal. The oxygen tube was excited at different V in the range of 2 to 5 kV of 50 cycles frequency. The discharge current i was observed with a sensitive mirror galvanometer actuated by a Cambridge vacuum junction (V. J., Fig. 1). The source of irradiations consisted of a battery of two 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulbs run at 200 volts. The mode of observation of Δi was essentially similar to that described in Part I of this series (Mohanty and Kamath, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 405). Data were obtained at different t between the room temperature, viz., 33° and 125° . In Table I, which represents but one typical set of observations, are shown the discharge current in dark i_0 , that under irradiation i_i , the net Joshi effect $\Delta i (=i_i - i_0)$ and the relative effect $\% \Delta i (=100 \Delta i / i_0)$ for various V and at different t .

DISCUSSION

These results show that at the lowest temperature, viz., 33° , Δi increases slowly with V . At a higher t , on the other hand, the corresponding increase in Δi is comparatively rapid. Thus e. g., Δi at 2.67 kV (r. m. s.) and 33° is 1.17. Increase of V to 3.2 kV enhances Δi to 1.54; a further rise in V to 4.27 kV raises Δi only to 1.75. At 75° , Δi increases from 1.06 at 2.67 kV to 2.03 at 4.27 kV. At 100° Δi attains a maximum (of 1.22) at 3.73 kV and decreases thereafter. The same behaviour is repeated at 125° . The relative effect $\% \Delta i$, however, decreases with V . At low t , there is at first a rapid and then a slow fall in $\% \Delta i$. Thus e. g., at 33° , whilst an increase of V from 2.67 to 3.2 kV decreases $\% \Delta i$ from 29.3 to 20.2, a further rise of V to 4.27 kV reduces $\% \Delta i$ only to 17.1. It is significant that at higher t , the initial decrease with V of $\% \Delta i$ is not precipitous, the diminution being slow and uniform over the entire potential range investigated. Thus, at 75° , increase of V from 2.67 to 4.27 kV reduces $\% \Delta i$ from 18.4 to only 12.9.

Temperature increases markedly both i_0 and i_i at constant V . Thus e. g., i_0 at 2.67 kV increases from 4.00 at 33° to 10.35 at 125° . Further, the rate of increase of i with t is initially small and becomes comparatively large at higher t . This behaviour is accentuated at higher applied V . Thus, whilst increase of t at 2.67 kV from 50°

to 75° enhances i_0 from 4.58 to 5.75, an equal increase of t from 100° to 125° raises i_0 from 7.14 to 10.35. At a higher V, e. g. 3.2 kV, i_0 increases from 9.59 to 10.58 and from 12.49 to 21.35 over the above ranges of t .

TABLE I

Influence of temperature on the Joshi effect in oxygen.

$pO_2=331$ mm. (32°). Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec. Source of irradiation = Two 200 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulbs, 22 cm. from the ozoniser Detector = Vacuo-junction.

V in kilo-volts (r. m. s.)		T e m p e r a t u r e				
		33°.	50°.	75°.	100°.	125°.
2.67	i_D	4.00	4.58	5.75	7.14	10.35
	i_L	2.83	3.32	4.69	6.6	9.85
	Δi	1.17	1.26	1.06	0.54	0.50
	% Δi	29.3	27.5	18.4	7.6	4.8
2.93	i_D	6.25	7.68	8.78	9.7	15.46
	i_L	4.8	6.25	7.42	8.94	14.93
	Δi	1.45	1.43	1.36	0.76	0.56
	% Δi	23.2	18.6	15.5	7.8	3.6
3.2	i_D	7.62	9.59	10.58	12.49	21.35
	i_L	6.08	7.94	9.03	11.45	20.81
	Δi	1.54	1.65	1.55	1.04	0.54
	% Δi	20.2	17.2	14.7	8.3	2.5
3.47	i_D	8.37	10.86	12.33	14.73	
	i_L	6.78	9.00	10.58	13.60	
	Δi	1.59	1.86	1.75	1.1	
	% Δi	19.0	17.1	14.2	7.5	
3.73	i_D	9.00	11.92	13.64	16.77	
	i_L	7.35	9.9	11.79	15.55	
	Δi	1.65	2.02	1.85	1.22	
	% Δi	18.3	16.8	13.6	7.3	
4	i_D	9.75	12.84	14.90	18.84	
	i_L	8.00	10.73	12.92	17.69	
	Δi	1.75	2.11	1.98	1.15	
	% Δi	18	16.4	13.3	6.1	
4.27	i_D	10.24	13.75	15.78	20.52	
	i_L	8.49	11.62	13.75	19.64	
	Δi	1.75	2.13	2.03	0.88	
	% Δi	17.1	15.5	12.9	4.3	

The increase of i with t might be due, in part, to the enhanced mobility of ions brought about in consequence of the thermal break-down of ion-clusters. That such clusters are formed in oxygen appears plausible from the following theoretical considerations due to Hassé (*Phil. Mag.*, 1926, vii, 1, 139): The condition for cluster formation is that the potential energy of the molecule in contact with the ion must be greater than the average kinetic energy of relative motion :

$$\frac{(\epsilon - 1)e^2}{8\pi n\sigma^4} / \frac{3}{2} RT = \frac{2}{3\lambda^2},$$

where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the gas; e , the ion charge; n , the number of molecules per unit volume; σ , the distance of closest approach at a collision between ion and molecules and $\lambda^2 = 8\pi p\sigma^4 / (\epsilon - 1)e^2$. The ratio $\frac{2}{3}\lambda^2$ determines cluster formation. For $\lambda < 0.8165$, as obtains in oxygen, clusters occur.

Ozone is formed but to a small extent under the experimental conditions. Its thermal decomposition might contribute to the observed increase with t of i . This is to be anticipated from the results of Pinkus and Ruysen (*Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1928, **37**, 304) who observed that the decomposition of 10^{-6} to 10^{-7} g. mol. of ozone per second in a field of 845 volts/cm. produces currents of 10^{-11} to 10^{-12} amp. The temperature coefficient of the thermal decomposition of ozone is high, viz., 2.5 (Warburg, *Ann. Physik*, 1903, **9**, 1286; Clement, *ibid.*, 1904, **14**, 334; Chapman and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 2463).

Data regarding the dependence of ionic mobility K on t are scarce. Much of the earlier investigations were conducted under conditions which are far from satisfactory. Phillips (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1905, **A**, **78**, 167) observed that the temperature variation of the mobility constant K , the mobility at the gas density ρ_0 at 0° and 760 mm. pressure, follows Sutherland's equation for viscosity. This, however, could not be substantiated by Kovaric (*Phys. Rev.*, 1910, **i**, **30**, 415) and Erikson (*ibid.*, 1914, **ii**, **5**, 151; 1915, **6**, 345). Later, Schilling (*Ann. Physik*, 1927, **83**, 23) tested the Sutherland law over a temperature range of 60° . Erikson's results which appear to be by far the best of the older work, covered a range from 400°A down to liquid-air temperatures. The mobility constant K altered but little, except at the lowest temperatures when it decreased by about 10%. Tyndall and Pearce (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1935, **A**, **149**, 426) and Pearce (*ibid.*, 1936, **A**, **155**, 490) investigated the variation of K for N_2^+ in N_2 gas, and for Na^+ and Cs^+ in He. Owing to charge transference, results for N_2^+ in N_2 are of less significance. In the case of Na^+ and Cs^+ in He, it was found that the increase of K with t was more marked under conditions of constant pressure than under conditions of constant density. Any sensible change in the latter, however, is excluded by conditions (viz., a sealed Siemens' tube) under which the Joshi effect is determined. Increase of K will consequently be small and cannot account for the large current rise observed, e.g. about three-fold over $33^\circ\text{-}125^\circ$ at 3.2 kV.

The increase with t of the dielectric conductivity of glass is also a possible contributory factor. On the modern theory, the electrons in a solid dielectric just fill an energy band at the absolute zero. At any higher t some of the electrons are thermally excited into the next unoccupied band. The number of electrons excited is of the form $e^{-b/T}$; b is connected with the energy-step between the two bands. Since these electrons are free to move through the lattice, they produce an electrical conductivity whose temperature variation is also of the form $e^{-b/T}$ (Wilson, "Semi-conductors and Metals", Cambridge Univ. Press, 1939). Experiment has shown (Whitehead, "Lectures on Dielectric Theory and Insulation", McGraw Hill, 1927) that the temperature variation of the final conductivity of glass obeys approximately the relation

$$I_t = I_0 e^{at},$$

where α is a constant. A corresponding change is observed in dielectric absorption of the substance.

Joshi (*Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19) has shown that

$$t = V \left/ \frac{1}{jC_w \sum f} + \frac{1}{1/R_g + jC_g \sum f} \right.,$$

where j is the operator ($=\sqrt{-1}$), C_w , the combined capacity of the inner and outer electrode walls of the ozoniser; C_g , the capacitance due to the enclosed gas; R_g , the latter's ohmic resistance; $\sum f$, the frequency not only of the A. C. supply and its harmonics, but also those produced under the discharge. Increase of t at constant V would result from a like change in one or more of the quantities C_w , C_g , $1/R_g$ and $\sum f$. The probable mechanism leading to an increase with t of the ohmic conductance $1/R_g$ (which depends on the number and velocity of the ions) has been considered (*vide supra*). Temperature increases appreciably the dielectric constant of glass (Gray and Dobbie, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1898, A, 63, 38; 1900, A, 67, 197), and hence also C_w . The dielectric constant of the gas (and hence C_g), on the other hand, decreases. This diminution is, however, small on account of the inappreciable reduction in the density of the enclosed oxygen. Besides, an increase in $\sum f$ with t is not unlikely.

The 'threshold potential' V_m (at which t increases markedly with the applied V), obtained by extrapolation of the $V-i_n$ curves, increases with t up to 50° and decreases thereafter. This is evident from the following results.

t	33°	50°	75°	100°	125°
V_m (in kilo-volts)	... 2.37	2.37	2.31	2.10	2.16
% Variation from 33°	...	+2.6	0.00	-5.2	-6.5

Opinion is divided on the dependence of electrical break-down strength of solid dielectrics on temperature. According to Inge, Semenov and Walther (*Archiv Elektrotechnik*, 1926, 17, 433), the break-down strength is independent of temperature. Buehl and von Hippel (*Phys. Rev.*, 1939, 56, 941) found, on the other hand, that for pure ionic crystals, the electronic break-down strength increases with t to a maximum and then decreases. The break-down path in these cases depends on the crystallographic orientation (von Hippel, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, 42 A, 78).

The net effect Δi at constant V increases with t up to 50° and then decreases. Thus *e. g.*, Δi at 3.2 kV and 33° is 1.54; it is 1.65 at 50° and 1.55 at 75° . Above 3.07 kV, Δi at 75° is larger than that at 33° ; below this potential, the reverse is the case. At 100° and 125° , Δi is markedly reduced, being only 1.04 and 0.54 respectively at 3.2 kV. The relative effect % Δi decreases progressively with t . Thus, at the above potential it is 20.2 at 33° and diminishes to 2.5 at 125° .

According to Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 26; 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 25; *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 15, 281; 1947, 16, 19), the formation on the excited electrodes of a boundary layer derived, in part, from a

wall-adsorption of ions and neutral molecules in the discharge space, is primary to Δi . Electrons released from this layer on irradiation are captured by the electronegative gas elements forming slow moving negative ions which reduce i by a space-charge effect. Heating would cause desorption and depolarization of the ions and the other particles constituting the electrode layer. Decrease in Δi with t , as observed, is therefore to be anticipated. It is also known (Huges and Dubridge, "Photo-electric Phenomena", McGraw Hill, 1932) that whilst photo-electron emission from pure metals increases with temperature, that from a surface film of a certain critical thickness deposited on a metal is reduced due to heating. At higher temperatures, the formation of negative ions may be inhibited leading to a decrease in Δi .

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